

Twenty years back, five years forward

The past, present and future of DANS

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DANS

IDCC 2025

The Hague, 19 February 2025

Two anniversaries

2025 International Digital Curation Conference

D C C

The logo features the year '2025' in white on a dark blue background. To its right, the words 'International Digital Curation Conference' are stacked in yellow and white. Below this, the letters 'D C C' are displayed in white, with a small graphic of three overlapping squares (orange, yellow, and white) to the left.

Data Archiving and Networked Services

DANS

The logo consists of the text 'Data Archiving and Networked Services' in red, italicized font above the word 'DANS' in large, blue, stylized letters. The letters 'D', 'A', and 'N' have unique cutouts. Below the letters are several small blue dots.

20 Years

A celebratory graphic featuring the number '20' in large blue font. A red box with the word 'Years' is placed over the '0'. The graphic is decorated with blue gears, a network of lines and dots, and a cluster of colorful balloons (purple, green, pink, blue, orange, white, and grey) on the right side.

DANS: the organisation

Predecessors

1964: The **Steinmetz archive** is founded on 27 November. This initiative can be considered the starting point of data archiving in the humanities and social sciences in the Netherlands.

2005: On 1 June, **Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)** is launched. The Steinmetz, NHDA, WSA and EDNA archives are merged into DANS, which starts to develop various new facilities.

1994: The **Scientific Statistical Agency (WSA)** is established with the aim of obtaining large data files from organisations such as Statistics Netherlands (CBS).

2004: Launch of the **E-depot of Dutch Archaeology (EDNA)**, an archive for electronic archaeological excavation data.

1987: The **Dutch Historical Data Archive (NHDA)** is initiated by the History and Informatics working group of Leiden University.

2005: DANS is born

Data Archiving and Networked Services

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2004 21 2005 2007

DANS

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Over DANS

Wat is DANS?

DANS is de nationale organisatie die zorgt voor de opslag en blijvende toegankelijkheid van onderzoeksgegevens in de alfa- en gammawetenschappen. DANS werkt daartoe samen met onderzoekers en bevordert samenwerking tussen hen onderling. DANS heeft de vorm van een netwerk, met een centrum dat verantwoordelijk is voor de organisatie van de data-infrastructuur. Dat centrum bestaat uit een team van ca. vijftien mensen die werken op het DANS-kantoor in Den Haag of bij één van de onderzoekcentra in het land. DANS is ook partner in internationale data-organisaties, zodat gegevensbestanden uit het buitenland gemakkelijk te verkrijgen zijn voor Nederlandse onderzoekers. DANS is in de zomer van 2005 met haar werk begonnen. Deels bestaat dat werk uit de activiteiten van data-archieven die al eerder bestonden; deels omvat het nieuwe activiteiten om een efficiënte infrastructuur voor opslag en toegang tot data van de grond te krijgen op gebieden die nog niet bestaan.

- [Waarom DANS?](#)
- [Taken van DANS](#)
- [DANS keurmerk](#)
- [Data-archieven](#)
- [Thematische Ontwikkelprogramma's](#)
- [Data-archiveringsprojecten](#)
- [Afzonderlijke overeenkomsten](#)
- [Organisatie en mensen](#)

DANS factsheet [pdf] (88 KB)

- ▶ Medewerkers
- ▶ (Inter-)nationale samenwerking
- ▶ DANS in de pers
- ▶ Nieuwsbrief Historia en Informatica

Why DANS
DANS tasks
DANS seal
Data archives
Thematic development programmes
Data archiving projects
Collaborations
Organisation and people

https://web.archive.org/web/20051221042638/http://www.dans.knaw.nl/nl/over_dans/

TDRs and FAIR data

.knaw.nl/nl/data_deponeren/dans_keurmerk/

Go

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2005 2006 20

Data Archiving and Network

2009

DANS

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DANS keurmerk

Digitale archieven hebben als doel om digitale informatie toegankelijk te houden voor toekomstig gebruik. Hoewel er duizenden digitale archieven in allerlei vormen bestaan, is er geen eenduidige strategie om de kwaliteit van digitale data te garanderen en deze data voor de lange termijn te bewaren en beschikbaar te stellen. Wel zijn er in de loop der tijd uiteenlopende handswijzen en gebruiken ontstaan die door digitale archieven worden gehanteerd. DANS heeft de opdracht aanbevelingen te doen voor criteria waaraan digitale archieven behoren te voldoen. Deze aanbevelingen zijn gebaseerd op onderzoek naar archiveringsmethoden en -technieken en evaluatie van internationale richtlijnen. Dit zal leiden tot een keurmerk met betrekking tot betrouwbaarheid op drie terreinen:

- betrouwbaarheid van de digitale data: *DANS-compliant data-quality*
- betrouwbaarheid bij het gebruik van de data: *DANS-compliant data-usage*
- betrouwbaarheid van digitale data-bewaarplaatsen: *DANS-compliant data-repository*

Factsheet keurmerk
▶ Data document

https://web.archive.org/web/20060104072030/http://www.dans.knaw.nl/nl/data_deponeren/dans_keurmerk/

DANS compliant data repository

DANS compliant data repository should:

- organize the assessment of the quality of the data files made available (if possible by peer review) and take measures to correct errors and inaccuracies in the data that are discovered afterwards: DANS compliant data quality.
- make data *findable, accessible and usable* at all times: DANS compliant data usage.
- manage and maintain data that are made available (i.e. *archive them in such a way that the data remains accessible in the long term*): DANS compliant data repository.

Repositories and trust

FAIR data

Home » Nieuws » [DANS-workshop op de Open Science FAIR in Athene](#)

DANS-workshop op de Open Science FAIR in Athene

4 augustus 2017

DANS organiseert in september een workshop op de Open Science FAIR met als titel 'FAIR Metrics – starring your datasets'.

Table of Contents

Glossary

Findable

1. No PID AND no metadata/documentation
2. PID present but without metadata/insufficient metadata
3. Sufficient metadata without PID
4. PID with sufficient metadata
5. Extensive metadata and rich additional documentation available

Accessible

1. Metadata nor data are accessible
2. Metadata are accessible but data is not accessible or no longer available
3. User restrictions apply
4. Public access (after registration - slightest restriction)
5. Open Access (unrestricted)

Interoperable

1. Proprietary, non-open format data
2. Proprietary format, accepted by Certified Trustworthy Data Repository
3. Non-proprietary, preferred open format (= “*preferred format*”)
4. As well as in the preferred format, data is additionally standardised using a standard vocabulary (for the research field to which the data pertain)
5. Dataset is additionally linked to other data to provide context

Final rating/review comments

Comment | [Open access](#) | Published: 15 March 2016

The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship

[Mark D. Wilkinson](#), [Michel Dumontier](#), [IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg](#), [Gabrielle Appleton](#), [Myles Axton](#), [Arie Baak](#), [Niklas Blomberg](#), [Jan-Willem Boiten](#), [Luiz Bonino da Silva Santos](#), [Philip E. Bourne](#), [Jildau Bouwman](#), [Anthony J. Brookes](#), [Tim Clark](#), [Mercè Crosas](#), [Ingrid Dillo](#), [Olivier Dumon](#), [Scott Edmunds](#),

> [Sci Data](#). 2018 Jun 26;5:180118. doi: 10.1038/sdata.2018.118.

A design framework and exemplar metrics for FAIRness

[Mark D Wilkinson](#)¹, [Susanna-Assunta Sansone](#)², [Erik Schultes](#)³, [Peter Doorn](#)⁴, [Luiz Olavo Bonino da Silva Santos](#)⁵ ⁶, [Michel Dumontier](#)⁷

Is your data

FAIR enough?

Checklist to evaluate FAIRness of data(sets)

TDRs and FAIR data into the future

Mission to keep data FAIR: is it still needed?

Hahnel, Mark; Smith, Graham; Schoenenberger, Henning; Scaplehorn, Niki; Day, Laura (2023). The State of Open Data 2023. Digital Science. Report. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24428194.v1>

TDRs and FAIR data into the future

Mission to keep data FAIR: is it still needed?

TDRs and FAIR data into the future

Mission to keep data FAIR: is it still needed?

The main findings of the report for publications from 2023 are:

- 44% of studied publications contain a data availability statement.
- 20% of publications mention data sharing.
- 16% of publications contain a formal citation to datasets.

- Encourage researchers to properly attribute and share datasets and software, leveraging best practices from disciplines where this is already common.
- Collaborate with repositories and publishers to improve metadata completeness for both dataset-to-publication and publication-to-dataset links.

TDRs and FAIR data into the future

Mission to keep data FAIR: is it still needed?

AI for FAIR

FAIR for AI

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Data Stations

305.847
datasets

Social
Sciences and
Humanities

Meer
informatie >>>

Archaeology

Meer
informatie >>>

Life Sciences

Meer
informatie >>>

Physical and
Technical
Sciences

Meer
informatie >>>

DataverseNL

Meer
informatie >>>

Data Archiving and Networked Services

DANS

20

Years

[Home](#) » [Data expertise](#)

Data expertise

Our expertise, built up in national and European projects, is reflected in the following expert services of DANS, intended for researchers, research institutions, research funders, data professionals and other archives, to help with (background information about) the sustainable storage and sharing of data.

FAIR and Open data
Make and keep your research data FAIR.

[Read more >>>](#)

Research Data Management
Manage all versions of your data efficiently and securely.

[Read more >>>](#)

Certification of digital archives
Meet the requirements for digital archives.

[Read more >>>](#)

Monitoring and analysis
DANS analyses information about the data landscape and makes this information available, which serves as a basis for data policy.

[Read more >>>](#)

Training and Outreach

A colorful illustration of a four-tiered pink and white birthday cake with yellow frosting and white stars. The cake is surrounded by colorful balloons (green, red, blue, yellow), streamers, and confetti. A red ribbon is draped across the base of the cake. In the background, there are stars and a blue arc at the top left.

Thank you for listening!

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Visit our website www.dans.knaw.nl

And follow us online

Mastodon @DANS_knaw_nwo

LinkedIn @DANS

X @DANS_knaw_nwo